

Ministry and Economic Prosperity, the 21st Century Challenges and Motivations into Ministry

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Abstract: This article investigated the nature of current practices in Christian ministry in Rwanda, which has recently been alleged for the commodification of the gospel due to a range of commoditization symptoms. An exploratory study has been carried out, just after the government of Rwanda initiated a new and solid legal environment allowing faith-based organizations to exercise their constitutional freedom, to examine factors that influence ministry, and understand Christian views about running a ministry for economic prosperity. The study has drawn a sample of 250 Christians from 10 local churches and 60 Christian leaders, approached through survey with an administered questionnaire. The findings revealed that the current social, political and economic environment isn't encouraging in terms of planting a new church. Most Christian leaders haven't attended any formal theological education or training, while Majority of theology students are in school due to the lack of secular education opportunities and the desire to become paid pastors in their churches. In addition, the majority of Christians did not know who makes the financial decisions in their churches, others understood that only senior pastors were entitled to this information, but most of them understood that giving to pastors is the key to unlock one's blessings. The study confirmed symptoms of prosperity gospel, along with other ministerial challenges, but recommended a return to ministry primarily as a sacrificial act rather than a recourse to the Gospelpreneurship.

Key words: Christianity in Rwanda, Prosperity Gospel, Gospelpreneurship, Factors Influencing Ministry, Economic Survival vs Economic Prosperity.

I. Introduction

1.1. Background to the study

Although the African continent is endowed with many natural resources, its inhabitants have long been among the poorest in the world (Arieff, 2015). While a few countries in sub-Saharan Africa are doing relatively well, most are plunged into poverty (Lebert, 2015). The abundance of natural resources in the African continent can, in many cases, have so little effect on the quality of life of its inhabitants for so many years (Sangwa, 2020). This is one of the great mysteries surrounding the consolidation of 49 nations in the south of the Sahara Desert.

Rwanda, one of the developing countries, is a nation of contrasts that presents few natural resources, but a growing economy (World Bank, 2019). With economic disparity being a Bible prophecy (Matthew 26:11; Deuteronomy 15:11) and a recurring global challenge, part of the population may naturally live in relative comfort and privilege, while others live in poverty or even extreme poverty. This gap between rich and poor is widening to worrying proportions living in inhumane conditions, with problems of unemployment and homelessness among others.

In terms of religion, the majority of Rwandans are Christians many of whom are ordinary people feeling or having a background of pain, inconvenience, shame and poverty prejudice. These conditions have affected many things in the practice of religion, especially Christianity where the very principle of the gospel has been thrown into the mud.

1.2. Problem statement

In the first place, most of the evangelical centers have been inundated with people, who do not necessarily come to receive Christian instruction and enlightenment, but rather become available

to seek a solution to their socio-economic problems. One has also observed that many people, especially young people and middle-aged graduates who find pleasure in modern worship, quickly find their place in the Church and claim to be called of God sooner or later often after some fruitless efforts to find employment.

Secondly, a range of people resort to pursuing theological education and/or to establishing Church ministry as instruments for economic profit. The question of Christians who, after significant financial and/or behavioral conflicts, left their churches [sometime after disciplinary sanctions] to establish new churches was important for some time. Many of these ministers have been criticized for having no theology or secular education, nor do they have real ministerial orientation. Similarly, many Christians would move from church to church looking for leadership positions or financial benefits; which can also predict a number of pretending Christians who are in churches and servicing in different ministerial departments but not born again Christians at all.

As a result, there has been a luxury increase in churches and venues for ministerial-led worships, often associated with the preaching of the material prosperity gospel that many people see as a way to amass personal wealth (Marshall, 2009; Asamoah-Gyadu, 2009; Angel, 2013; Chitando, Gunda, & Kügler, 2013). These practices leave critical and cynical observers speaking contemptuously of "*Gospelpreneurship*" (Chitando et al. 2013; News24, 2015) to lament that the Christian gospel has become a commodity that can turn into a form of lucrative entrepreneurship.

The end result is that the image of Church ministers has radically changed from traditional anti-materialist and paradise-centric clergy to materialist and, why not, what the authors of The Herald (2014) called glamorous clergy who invest in the stock markets and amass enough wealth to compete for the list of the richest people. In contrast to the traditional model where becoming a

pastor is to respond to the heavenly spiritual call and to renounce the world, the present model of the entrepreneur presents a true spirituality and a true ministry authenticated by socio-economic progress.

1.3. Study objectives

1.3.1. The general objectives

This study aimed to collect different views on obstacles facing Christian Business Administration in Rwanda, *and* explore gaps in public or ministerial policies in order to recommend what can be done to maintain the authenticity of Christian ministry.

1.3.2. Specific objectives

1. To examine the social, political and economic factors that influence the Christian ministries in Rwanda
2. To examine the influence of theology education and training on the development of Christian business /ministry
3. To understand Christian views about running a ministry for economic prosperity

1.4. Methods

This study used an exploratory approach to investigate Christian understanding of one of the negative Christian behaviors/responses in the context of poverty: “*running a ministry for economic prosperity.*” Different active Christians, pastors and aspiring Christian ministers were approached. This survey was limited to ten (10) churches operating in Nyanza District, Rwanda. The study focused on the opinions of Christians who perform various services in the ministerial departments

of their churches. The Christians selected for the study were to be members of the church for at least two years. For qualitative data, the study focused on department heads, pastors and leaders of churches recently closed by the government.

II. Literature review

2.1. Introduction and context

Christianity is the largest religion in Rwanda, where the majority of citizens are Catholic or Protestant Christians, alongside smaller Muslim populations (Gregory, 2017). The most recent statistics on religion, released by the National Institute of Statistics of Rwanda (NISR, 2012), reports that: 45.4% of the Rwanda's population is Roman Catholic, 37.3% is Protestant, 11.9% is Adventists, 1.1% is Muslim (mainly Sunni), 4.2% claims no or other religious affiliation, and practices traditional indigenous beliefs.

Religion in Rwanda dates back so long to the pre-colonial period as the monarchy was bound by the indigenous Rwandan religion, which considered the king to be of divine origin. The power and authority of the king were spiritual in origin (Chrétien, 2003; Vansina, 2004). In addition to the religion associated with the royal court, Rwandans worshiped a wide range of ancestral spirits and minor deities, offering sacrifices to influence the spirit world in their favor.

According to Ward (2008), Christianity in Rwanda dates back to the German colonial period when the Catholic White Fathers first established their mission in 1900. New societies then entered the country, especially Seventh-day Adventists and the Anglicans (the "Rwanda Mission"). However, the German Lutherans were expelled during the First World War, after which Rwanda became a Belgian mandate of the League of Nations. A Belgian Protestant missionary society took over the German mission stations. All these missions sought converts among Rwandans of all

categories, but Catholics remained the main beneficiaries of the official support of Mwami Musinga, King of Rwanda, and the Belgian colonial authorities. Although religion was accused of playing a crucial role in the genocide perpetrated against the Tutsi in 1994, the Christian church also has an incredible role to play in the restoration of the Post-genocide Rwanda (Bazuin, 2013).

In Rwanda after the genocide, churches remain powerful institutions. They are important for promoting healing and reconciliation among Rwandans, for dealing with the trauma and guilt of the genocide, and for helping to develop structures to overcome the burden of ethnic division. The Catholic Church continues to be the church of the majority of Rwandans; Anglicans benefited from the new Anglophone regime, whose leaders were trained in Uganda and were often members of the (Anglican) Church of Uganda. But the new Pentecostal churches are currently growing rapidly, also transforming the worship and spirituality of the old churches.

Sudden increase of Christian churches in Rwanda

In particular, the last decade has seen an exponential increase in the number of Christian churches. For example, according to a report by the Rwanda Governance Board (RGB), the number of recognized religious denominations was less than 10 in 1962, but rose to 50 and 350 in 1994 and 2012 respectively. Surprisingly, since 2012, when the new law governing faith-based organizations came into effect, and in 2017, the number of officially registered religious organizations had increased to more than 1,000 within these five years (RGB, 2017). The 2018 also emerged lavishly new religious organizations with numerous worship places throughout the countrywide. This rapid growth forced the government to put in place a solid legal environment allowing faith-based organizations to exercise their constitutional freedom. The government then closed more than 6,000 churches, mosques and other places of worship in February 2018, which

it found in violation of health and safety standards and / or noise pollution ordinances (USA Report 2018, Himbara, 2019). According to the RGB (2018), the closures do not infringe on freedom of worship, but rather target the alarming proliferation of places of worship in dilapidated and unsanitary conditions, as well as the disturbing behavior of unscrupulous individuals posing as religious leaders. The latter, among other abuses, defrauded innocent followers, spread insults against women and other religions, and forced followers to fast to starvation.

2.2. Commoditization of ministry

The rise of Christian ministry practices emphasizing wealth and prosperity has globally been associated with the commoditization and commodification of Christian ministry. According to Magezi & Banda (2017), Church ministry was used as instrument for economic profit. While the Bible encourages Christians to work and make profit, for example in the Parable of the Talents where Jesus approves of profiting by investment (Matthew 25); the Gospel should freely be preached to all people. According to (Benyah, 2018), the contemporary practice of pursuing ministry as a means of economic gain is symptomatic of the commodification and commercialization of religion. This detrimental situation may confirm the belief of humanists that our current desire to win and a profit-driven society has proven inadequate and that a radical change in methods, controls and motives must be instituted.

In Rwanda, conflicts within churches have multiplied over the past decade, leading to the proliferation of new churches (RwandaToday, 2018). Most of these conflicts are related to the mismanagement of the ministry's finances (Huaxia, 2018). While the right to religion and freedom of worship are guaranteed by the Rwandan constitution, the Rwandan Government has noticed an

alarming proliferation of places of worship in dilapidated and unhygienic conditions, as well as troubling behaviour of unscrupulous individuals masquerading as religious leaders.

From the above practices, the question is whether Christian ministry and theological education should be pursued in the hope of economic gain.

2.3. Ministry as a sacrificial act

Traditionally, commitment to Christian ministry is seen as a personal sacrifice that projects ministry as a difficult, costly, and materially thankless calling (Magezi & Banda, 2017). That's why ministry did not attract people who expected financially lucrative careers. Beidelman (1981) supports this idea and points out that "*missionaries have often described their work as an act of sacrifice or as a means to perfect their character*". This description is evident in many missionaries who have endured many personal struggles in the mission realm (Ransford, 1968; Hastings, 1994), persevering amid irrelevant results (Lovett, 1899) and facing death and being buried far from their close relatives (Thomas, 1873). An important part of the description was the lack of material gain and the provision of service to desperate people at the expense of the Christian minister.

As Isichei (1995) points out, missionaries in Africa, especially those in rural areas, served mainly the poor who could not receive more than they could repay. Thus, venturing into the unknown dark lands of Africa was viewed in heroic terms. The fact that missionary work does not have the material benefits of economic enrichment, but a life of austerity and altruism, characterized by survival with minimal resources rather than the accumulation of material wealth and self-aggrandizement, in order to serve and save lost humanity with a high degree of commitment and sacrifice; imposes the obligation to consider missionary service as a vocation and not as a profession (as a spiritual call and not as a job).

Magezi & Banda (2017) understand that such a solemn vision of ministry encouraged missionaries to cherish their vocation by affirming its solemnity and uniqueness compared to other professions. It was in fact a privatized expression of faith based on a dualistic view of reality, dualistically distinguishing the things of the world from the spiritual things and therefore projected the material things as secular to the point of lacking God and the spiritual things as pious. It gave the impression that faith was useful in a privatized context detached from material things and did not have an integrated approach between spiritual and material things. Many evangelical Christian churches have emerged with an emphasis on a doctrine of holiness and anti-materialism, a bigotry that rejected the many pleasures and luxuries of everyday life (Maxwell, 2006). However, starting a ministry was based on faith in God's ability to provide whatever the minister materially needed.

Magezi & Banda (2017) concluded that the sacrificial view of Christian ministry tended to be applied to Africans without paying attention to the economic disparity between white missionaries and African ministers. Their conclusion was based on the Gondongwe (2011) record where Zimbabwean Methodist authorities expressed their extreme dismay that African Methodist youth had avoided the ministry call due to low salaries. In this record, a Methodist superintendent was recorded giving his horrified take on Africans' rejection of the appeal to the ministry declaring: *"The whole argument ranged round money. There may be other reasons but I am led to the conclusion that the African expects his job to pay"*. This statement reflects the idea that it is wrong to expect the economic survival of a post in a ministry. To some extent, the expectation of a steady income is seen as a sign of reluctance to serve sacrificially, as well as a lack of dependence and faith in God. In addition, the hope of economic survival seemed to be a form of materialism. And yet, what appeared to be a sacrificial act for missionaries, appeared to be an act of luxury for poor Africans (Beidelman, 1981; Gondongwe, 2011; Oliver, 2016).

2.4. The shift from ministry as a sacrificial act to economic prosperity

According to Magezi & Banda (2017), the shift from ministry as a sacrificial act to the conception of Christian ministry as a means of economic prosperity is linked to the rise and growth of the prosperity gospel on the continent. Since then, the notion of ministry as a sacrificial act has been rejected and ministry has been asserted as a blessed profession which must have immediate and lucrative benefits for its workers (Marshall, 2009). Therefore, not as a renunciation of the world, but as emphasized by the entrepreneurial movement to hold the world. Likewise, Marshall-Fratani (1998) explained that instead of denying oneself and emphasizing austerity, the modern movement emphasizes self-indulgence and luxury by propagating a doctrine of morally controlled materialism, in which personal wealth and success are interpreted as the proof blessing for those who lead a true life in Christ.

Maxwell (2006) points out that in some situations the most significant change has ironically been motivated not by the emergence of new movements, but by the shift from traditional anti-materialist movements from holiness to this worldly materialist orientation. As an example, he mentioned that in the 1970s evangelism was the burning passion of the Assemblies of God Africa Pastorate in Zimbabwe (ZAOGA), but later in the 1990s the main concern of pastors was related to their material well-being. This is evident in Bishop Ezekiel Guti's speech:

If you don't want to die or leave and get poor, or have little kids mock you in the streets, then stay and grow rich. People who have left do not prosper, they lose their blessings. When they get old they have nothing. It takes time to build a church and to start making money.¹

¹ Maxwell, D., 2006, *African gifts of the spirit: Pentecostalism & the rise of a Zimbabwean transnational religious movement*. Page 154

This message conveyed the idea that Christian ministry guaranteed economic prosperity, therefore, those who abandoned ZAOGA's ministry were beyond the reach of material blessing. This means that joining the ministry of ZAOGA was a means of economic prosperity or in other words, his church which was part of his ministry was the blessing of the poor to raise them from their ashes and polish them to improve their acceptability in the country.

While Togarasei (2005) points out that the church can easily [be] mistake [n] for the shift from "*ministry as a service*" to "*ministry as entrepreneurship*". Marshall (2009) is very attached to the fact that establishing a church and "*doing God work has become a means of accumulating personal wealth and personal dominance these days.*" According to him (Marshall), doing God's work is now seen as a "*brand*" marketed through a wide range of props, such as TV ads that can compete with commercial product ads, armbands, t-shirts, , water bottles and illuminated billboards, along major urban roads bearing the colorful images of the church leader with his wife.

On the other hand, Marshall (2009) observed that the organizational model of many churches has come to resemble more and more that of small (or large) private companies and an internal economy developed on the basis of a faith shared and new networks. While in most Zimbabwean churches, ministry activities were associated with secondary income-generating activities such as the sale of media productions, Bible colleges, private universities, banks, medical clinics and online subscriptions to line, about 80% of established churches and ministries believed that the late 1980s and 1990s had become the de facto private property of their founding leaders.

Arguably, in this business model of making the church, the founding prophet or pastor acts as the CEO or president of a personal business. Magezi and Banda (2017) analyzed the current model of the entrepreneurial church and found that church leaders adhering to the entrepreneurial model

of ministry exercise an oligarchical style of leadership that logically reduces the faithful to the commodity of leaders while leaving leaders accountable to no one except themselves. And because the founding leaders are the ambassador of their “*brand*” model, any criticism of the “*ministry*” or its appointed leader is met with a strong reaction, because it is ultimately an attack against the brand (Togarasei, 2005). It can be noted that the succession plan for leaders, in this type of ministry, is generally oriented around the close relatives of the founding leader, since most of them are registered as private companies.

The idea of making ministry a means of economic prosperity centers on the mediating power of the pastor as a channel of God's blessing for the Christian believer. Prophet Urbert Angel (2013), one of the main Zimbabwean supporters of this gospel, boldly affirmed this point by commanding Christians who yearn for wealth to generously plant their seed for a good harvest on fertile soil by giving magnanimously their money to anointed pastors. According to Angel (2013), the key to unlocking the blessing of riches is not giving to the poor, offering and tithing to the church. Rather, the key to wealth is to give to God's anointed people, especially men of God, with great anointing (Angel, 2013). In support of this, Angel understands that the widow of Zarephath (1 Kings 17: 7-24) was saved from an almost starving death because she emptied her last food stores on God's prophet Elijah. Indeed, most prosperity gospel preachers teach that invisible faith should lead to tangible financial rewards; therefore, wealth is seen as a blessing from God the provider. Magezi & Banda (2017) observed that the prosperity gospel would go further and claim that the size of your wallet indicates the size of your faith. Most prosperity gospel preachers would argue that prosperity is governed by a spiritual law of positive confession.

In summary, this model shows how the ministry has moved from providing sacrificial services to an investment whose returns are to be reaped immediately in this lifetime. Thus, the ministry

has become a channel for the accumulation of wealth. From the above discussion, the question that arises is the relationship between the exercise of the ministry and the economic benefits to the minister.

2.5. The Biblical Distinction between Economic Survival and Economic Prosperity in Ministry

Biblical teachings distinguish Christian ministry as an instrument of economic survival and ministry as a service instrument from which the minister can expect to earn economic survival.

There is a distinction between personal enrichment outside of ministry and being properly rewarded for ministry. A fundamental principle that runs through the Bible is that people have the right to survive economically through their work, including those in ministry. Torah said: "*Thou shalt not muzzle the ox when he treadeth out the corn*" (Deuteronomy 25: 4). This principle was applied to Levite priests to emphasize that priests should derive income from their priestly work (Deuteronomy 18: 1). Jesus observed the principle of not muzzling the ox while treading the grain in Luke 10: 1-24, when he sent 72 disciples, but forbade them to take provisions, telling them to survive on what their hosts could give them. The reason is that "*the worker deserves his wages*" (Luke 10,7).

The apostle Paul called on these two principles in 1 Corinthians 9 and 1 Timothy 5:18 to affirm the right of ministers of the gospel to receive economic support for their ministries. Paul defended the right of ministers to expect and receive financial support for their ministerial work in the church (1 Corinthians 9: 9-12). According to Zimmermann (2012), Paul's questions in 1 Corinthians 9 are ethical questions about: What is good behavior? What is it right and right to do and why? This body of evidence from biblical command and observable life situations shows that it is ethically

right that those who have undertaken ministerial work receive material support (Zimmermann, 2012). For Paul material well-being was important, but not important enough to hinder the ministry. Here is Zimmermann's (2012) explanation of what Paul's conduct means:

The key to everything must be for us what it was for Paul – ‘nor hindrance to the gospel’. For every valid ministry in the church of Jesus Christ this must be the bottom of line. All too often, one fears, the objective of this text is lost in concerns over ‘rights’ that reflect bald professionalism rather than a concern for the gospel itself.²

However, in the absence of material support from the congregation, Paul's option was not to resign himself to poverty. Instead, since the ministry was a top priority, he used his extra-economic skills to gain material well-being. So he could confidently say to Christians: "*Yea, ye yourselves know, that these hands have ministered unto my necessities, and to them that were with me*" (Acts 20:34). For Paul, commitment to the gospel, not money, dictated and shaped his ministerial ethics and practice. As a result, Paul shows us a minister who benefits from his ministerial work and not a minister who seeks to profiteer out of the ministry.

It can be concluded that the Bible does not view ministry as an instrument of economic gain. This means that participation in ministry should not be motivated by financial or material gain, but by service that transforms and heals the broken world (Oliver 2016: 1). On the contrary, those who choose Christian ministry have a right to expect economic survival. Therefore, there are Bible warnings about these false teachers who teach the false gospel "*for the sake of dishonest gain*" (Titus 1:11). In addition, elders are instructed to become diligent shepherds who are not "*in love*

² Zimmermann, R., 2012, ‘Mission versus ethics in 1 Corinthians 9? ‘Implicit ethics’ as an aid in analysing New Testament texts’, *HTS Theological Studies* 68(1), 211–219.

with money" (1 Timothy 3: 3) and *"not greedy for money"* (1 Peter 5: 3). These Scriptures condemn those who enter the ministry as a means of earning money. Jesus solemnly told his disciples that no one could serve God and Mammon (Matthew 6:24).

The eschatological nature of Christian ministry is a fundamental element of ministry as an instrument of service, even at sacrificial levels. Christian ministry is motivated by the quest for the Kingdom of God, which will be fully consummated upon Christ's final return but is already present in this world defying the kingdom of darkness that inflicts death (Conradie, 2001; Harvie, 2009). Christian ministry forbids growing materialism, for as an eschatological work the Christian minister works in his world - even at sacrificial levels - with the assurance that there is a better reward to be received at the final consummation of the Kingdom of God.

III. Findings and Interpretation

3.1. Introduction

This chapter presents the analysis, presentation and interpretation of data collected from participating Christians, Christian leaders and theology students in Rwanda. The study sampled 150 Christian from 10 churches operating in Nyanza District, 30 students and graduates in theology and 20 Christian leaders, as well as 10 former Christian leaders with churches closed by the government in early 2018 for regulatory reasons. The data were interpreted according to the research questions. The analysis was performed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The results were presented in the form of frequency tables and percentages.

3.2. Questionnaire return rate

Of the 150 questionnaires sent to the Christian leaders in the study, 143 were returned, giving a response rate of 95.3%. We have also achieved 100% of questionnaire return rate for the other categories, i.e. 30 questionnaires from theology students and graduates in theology and 20 from Christian leaders, and 10 from former Christian leaders with churches closed by the government in early 2018 for regulatory reasons. Although some questions were shared by all categories of the respondents, these late 60 Christian leaders and aspiring leaders were given specific leadership questions.

3.3. Characteristics of respondents

3.3.1. Composition of respondents by age and gender

Age	Gender				Total	Percent
	Female	Percent	Male	Percent		
18 -25	21	61.8	13	38.2	34	23.8
26 - 40	28	70.0	12	30.0	40	27.9
41 - 55	31	57.4	23	42.6	54	37.7
56 - 65	9	60.0	6	30.0	15	10.5

Table 3.1: Composition of respondents by Age and gender

The data in Table above show that Female Christians are likely to participate in ministerial church activities start their own business compared to their female counterparts. At a mature age, there are also more women (70% and 57.4%) respondents than men (30% and 42.6%). This aligns with Oxford University Press's (2009) point that women are more active in Christian churches than men. However, this can also be explained by the Rwandan tragedy, where a large number of men were massacred during the genocide perpetrated against the Tutsi in Rwanda in 1994. Similarly, another significant number of men perpetrators of the genocide were sentenced to life/long imprisonment.

3.3.2. Composition of respondents by education level

The chart below shows the educational attainment achieved by participating Christians or in which they were enrolled during the study period.

	Frequency	Percentage
University	14	10%
Secondary	75	52%
Primary	29	20%
Vocational/technical	21	15%
None	4	3%

Table 3.2: Respondents Education Levels

The level of Christian education was measured to determine if education can influence their active participation in ministry activities. The data in the above table shows that a majority (52%)

of Christians have completed high school education and primary school (20%). It can be argued from the findings that education level influences the level of participation in Christian ministry because 52% of participating Christians had attended secondary school; yet a recent population and Housing Census conducted by Rwanda National Institute of statistics (NISR, 2012) indicates that that Rwandans are generally educated at primary (57%) or secondary (11%) and few (2%) reach university. Education thus offers the opportunity to read and study the fundamentals of Christianity and to increase the self-confidence necessary to participate in religious and socio-economic programs.

3.3.3. Type of Ministry activities

The chart below shows the type of activity in which participating Christians were engaged in during the study period.

	Frequency	Percentage
Choir	18	13%
Deacon	24	17%
Group Leader	22	15%
Preacher / Intercessor	28	20%
Preparing for Baptism	22	15%
Member of an internal committee	20	14%

Other	9	6%
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Table 3.3: Type of Church Activities

The fact that respondents are Christians engaged in different ministerial services ensures that the data collected provides a complete view of Christian understanding on various topics.

3.4. Social, political and economic factors that influence the Christian ministries in Rwanda

3.4.1. Influence of social factors

As Christians have potential influence on the social environment (Hope & Jones, 2014 ; Graham, 2019) also argues that the first influence that may promote our obedience to God, is society. The social environment is the first influence which affects Christians, especially ministers who decide to engage in unpaid or sacrificial ministry. An encouraging social environment guarantees the commitment and sustainability of Christian ministry. The table below presents respondents' opinions on their social environment and Christian ministry.

	Frequency	Percentage
Encouraging	72	35.5%
Discouraging	131	64.5%

Table 3.4: Influence of Social Environment

According to the data presented above, a sizeable proportion of the respondents (64.5%) revealed that their social environment was not encouraging with 35.4% disclosing it was encouraging.

3.4.2. Government policy and regulations

While Christians Should Seek to Influence Government for Good (Wayne, 2018), government policies and regulations may also affect Christian or ministry decisions, activities, especially when these policies are not favourable. As sojourners and exiles (1 Peter 2:11), it can be tempting for Christians to adopt a mind-set that earthly governing systems are inconsequential to the task of furthering the gospel. Like Crossway (2018) puts it, God established civil government as a blessing to human beings, to protect us against the great evil of anarchy. Governments should punish evil and encourage good, executing justice on wrongdoers and defending the weak and defenceless. The church should obey the laws of the government.

Christians leaders surveyed were asked if they see or thought that government regulations were difficult to comply with by Christians willing to set up / run a church / Christian ministry in Rwanda.

	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	28	46.67%
Agree	19	31.67%
Neutral	8	13.33%
Disagree	5	8.33%
Strongly Disagree	0	0%

Table 3.5: Compliance with Government Policies

According to the data collected from Christian leaders and theology scholars presented in the above table, 46.67% strongly agreed that the current government policies and regulations are difficult, for Christian leaders, to comply with when trying to set up or run a Christian ministry in Rwanda. On the same question, 31.67% of respondent agreed and 13.33% remained neutral to the statement. However, 8.33% of respondent disagreed on this statement but none strongly disagreed on it.

3.4.3. Regulatory challenges for Christian ministries

All Christians surveyed, [former] Christian leaders and theological students were asked to evaluate, according to their understanding, the different regulatory challenges that Christian ministers face when initiating or running a church / ministry. The chart below provides results of their responses.

	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Education Requirements	29	48%
Building Standards	17	28%
Registration Procedures	5	8%
Lots of Documents	6	10%
Others	3	5

Table 3.6: Regulatory Challenges

A big number of respondent indicated that the education requirements (48%) and building standards required (28%) to establish a church ministry in Rwanda are the main regulatory

challenges that Christian ministers face. However, 8% of respondents also highlighted challenge in registration processes, 10% indicating that the requirements of lots of documents while 5% see other challenges than these.

3.5. Theology education and training on Christian ministry

3.5.1. Access to theology education

The below figure shows the percentage of Christian leaders who, prior to starting their church/ ministry, had received any form theology education at any academic institution.

	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Yes	22	36.67%
No	38	63.33%

Table 3.7: Access to Theology Education before starting ministry

The data presented in the table shows that majority of Christian leaders (63.3%) had not received any form of academic theology education prior to starting/ engaging in Christian Ministry. However, 36.7% had been academically trained.

To understand if Christian leaders had opportunities for theology training outside academic institutions, respondents were asked if they had ever been through any kind of theology training program since you began your ministry and the below figure shows the results:

<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
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Yes	41	68.33%
No	19	31.67%

Table 3.8: Access to Theology training after starting ministry

The results presented in the table indicate that majority (68.3%) of the surveyed Christian leaders had had opportunities to attend a form on theology training given institutions, whereas 31% had never been trained on theology.

3.5.2. Appropriate level of education to become a Christian leader

In order to understand the value that Christian leaders place on secular education / training, respondents were asked to give their opinions on the level of education deemed appropriate to become a Christian leader. The figure below presents the answers:

	Frequency	Percentage
No Schooling Needed	8	13.33%
Primary	15	25%
Secondary	31	51.67%
University	6	10%

Table 3.9: Level of education needed to become a minister

According to the data presented above, the majority of respondents (51.67%) understand that secondary education is enough to become a Christian leader. Another sizeable number (25%) mentions that the world of primary schools is appropriate for directing Christian ministry.

However, 10% mention the need for a university degree, while 13.3% say that no schooling would be necessary to lead the Christian community.

3.5.3. Motivations to study theology

To understand the underlying motivations of theology students, a specific question was asked of 30 randomly selected theology students in various Protestant institutions.

	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Lack of Job	4	13.33%
Lack of secular education opportunities	10	33.33%
To be able to start my own church	5	16.67%
To Supplement my Income	2	6.67%
Divine Call	1	3.33%
To a Pastor at my Church	8	26.67%

Table 3.10: Motivation to study theology

The data presented above show that the majority of theology students are in school due to the lack of secular education opportunities (33.3%) and the desire to become pastors in their churches (26.67%). Some students (16.67%) are motivated by meeting the government's training requirements to start their own church ministry. While 13.33% chose theology because of lack of employment, 6.67% wish to supplement their income with a degree in theology. Surprisingly, only 3.33% feel a divine calling to the ministry.

3.5.4. Economic and Entrepreneurial Content in the Theology Curriculum

To understand if theology universities have entrepreneurial foundations, 30 theology students were asked if their program programs include enough courses in economics and entrepreneurship that could allow a graduate to start / run a successful business in a secular world. The results are presented below:

	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Yes	19	63.33%
No	11	36.67%

Table 3.11: Entrepreneurship content in theology programs

According to the results presented above, majority of respondents (63.33%) find that their programs lack adequate knowledge in economics and entrepreneurship, while 36.67% had these contents in their theology programs.

3.5.5. Mandatory Theology Education

A focus group discussion was held with Christian leaders to discuss if theology education should be a requirement to become a Christian leader. The majority of participants agreed that theological education was necessary for ministers of different abilities, but reflected the fact that some ministers did not have the opportunity to attend secular schools or theological education; yet they claim to have a Spiritual calling.

3.6. Christian views about running a ministry for economic prosperity

This part was intended to explore Christian views and the practices in their churches about running Christian ministry for economic prosperity.

3.6.1. Financial management and Pastors accountability

Magezi & Banda (2017) observed that most of the prosperity gospel ministers tend to register their churches as private companies where the leadership succession plan, in such kind of ministry, is commonly oriented around the close relatives of the founding leader, since they are registered as private companies. Furthermore, in these types of churches, financial decisions are centered on one individual or a group of individuals known of founders (Magezi & Banda, 2017).

In order to understand these practices, Christian respondents were asked to say who they think is the overall financial decision-maker (s) in their church and the answers are presented below.

	Frequency	Percentage
I don't know	59	41.26%
Administrative Team	19	13.29%
Senior Pastor	34	23.78%
An Elected committee	31	21.68%

Table 3.12: Financial decision-makers in church

The data collected indicates that most Christians (41.26%) are not aware of how financial decisions are made in their churches. While 23.78% attribute these responsibilities to senior pastors, 21.68% understand that financial decisions are made by their elected committee in their

church. Finally, the rest (13.29%) of the respondents point out that the final word on the financial decision belongs to the church's administrative team.

3.6.2. Religion and Marketplace linkage

Many prosperity preachers would tell Christian that the Bible condemns the accumulation of money, which [money] is described as a source of all evil on the planet. They would tell them to make extremely high offerings to win God's favor, but they would not even teach their followers how to make money. To test Christian understanding on this subject, a specific question was asked as to whether, to the best of their knowledge, the Bible condemns the accumulation of money.

	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	121	84.62%
No	22	15.38%

Table 3.13: Does the Bible condemn accumulation of money?

As it can be observed in the above data, many Christian (84.62%) understand that the accumulation of money is condemned by the Bible, while only 15.38% contracted the statement.

3.6.3. Prosperity Gospel and accumulation of wealth by Pastors

Like Urbert Angel (2013) emphasizes, the idea of making ministry a means of economic prosperity centers on the pastor's power of mediation as a channel of God's blessing for the Christian believer. The supporters of this gospel, boldly affirmed this point by commanding Christians who yearn for wealth to plant their seed generously for a good harvest on fertile soil by giving their money to anointed pastors magnanimously (Urbert Angel, 2013). To establish a

relationship with the wealth teaching above, Christian respondents were asked whether they agree or not that that giving God's anointed people, like pastors, brings more blessing from God.

	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Yes	85	59.44%
No	58	40.56%

Table 3.14: Giving to pastors unlocks one's blessings

Majority of Christian respondents (59.44) agreed that giving to God's People with great anointment, like pastors, unlocks the blessings of riches, while 40.56% disagreed on this statement.

3.7. Summary and Discussions

The purpose of this study was to examine the social, political and economic factors that influence the Christian ministries in Rwanda, the influence of theology education and training on the development of Christian Business/ ministry and to Understand Christian views about running a ministry for economic prosperity. Based on the responses provided by the respondents, the researcher generated results that were used to draw conclusions and make recommendations. The main conclusions are based on the results of the data analysis in the previous Chapter, as shown in the summary table.

Summary table

Objectives	Findings
1. Examine the social, political and economic factors that influence the Christian ministries in Rwanda	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Majority of the respondents (64.5%) revealed that their social environment was not ministerial encouraging with 35.4% disclosing it was encouraging. ✓ 46.67% of respondents strongly agreed and 31.67% agreed that the current government policies and regulations are difficult, for Christian leaders, to comply with when trying to set up or run a Christian ministry in Rwanda. ✓ Majority of respondent indicated that the education requirements (48%) and building standards required (28%) to establish a church ministry in Rwanda are the main regulatory challenges that Christian ministers face.
2. To examine the influence of theology education and training on the development of Christian Business/ ministry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 63.3% Christian leaders had not received any form of academic theology education prior to starting/ engaging in Christian Ministry, while only 36.7% had been academically trained ✓ 68.3% of Christian leaders attended a form on theology training after starting ministry whereas 31% had never been trained on theology. ✓ Majority of theology students are in school due to the lack of secular education opportunities (33.3%) and the desire to become a paid pastors in their churches (26.67%). Only 3.33% of surveyed theology students feels a divine call for ministry. ✓ Majority of respondents (63.33%) find that their programs lack adequate knowledge in economics and entrepreneurship, while 36.67% had these content in their theology programs.
3. Understand Christian views about running a ministry for economic prosperity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ 41.26% Christians don't know who takes financial decisions in their churches; 23.78% mentions senior pastors; 21.68% mentions their elected committee and 13.29% mentions church's administrative team. ✓ Majority of respondents (84.62%) understand that the accumulation of money is condemned by the Bible, while only 15.38% contradicted the statement. ✓ Majority of Christian respondents (59.44%) agreed that giving to pastors unlocks the blessings of riches, while 40.56% disagreed on this statement.

3.8. Discussions

3.8.1. Christian ministries and social, political and economic factors

Socio-economic factors can have different influences on the development of Christian ministry. Based on the result of the study, it's clear that the majority of respondents (64.5%) indicated that their social environment did not encourage them to engage in Christian ministry, compared to 35.4% of respondents having a supportive environment.

These results align with what Magezi and Banda (2017) who point out that Christian ministry tends to shift from sacrificial act to economic prosperity. Engagement in Christian ministry has long been traditionally seen in terms of sacrifice that make the ministry a difficult and expensive project and vocation materially unrewarding. Beidelman (1981:83) points out that missionaries “often described their work as an act of sacrifice or as means of refining character”. This lack of material gains and the provision of services to desperate people to the detriment of the servant were not welcome in the Rwandan community, which beyond other good reasons, leads to the Magezi and Banda's (2017) conclusion that the African expects his job to pay. Therefore, knowing that the ministry has never attract people who expected to be lucrative careers, one can conclude that neither the family nor the entire social environment would encourage people to engage in Christian ministry as an unpaid or less paid career.

On the other hand, 46.67% and 31.67% of respondents strongly agreed and agreed respectively that current government policies and regulations are difficult for Christian leaders to meet when trying to create or manage a Christian ministry in Rwanda. To approach these results, it's important to highlight that no religious nor political world can remain the same forever, it is subject to transformative processes that respond to the needs of the community. New policies, regulations,

places, roles and powers are recognized, while old policies, regulations, places, roles and powers acquire new meanings (Lawson, 1984). The recent law of the Rwandan government determining the organization and functioning of faith-based organizations may have effects on various socio-economic and political factors on religious activity. However, one must acknowledge that the story of the Rwandan community needs to be understood within its own unique political and cultural context (Prozesky, 1995). So what is the Rwandan context? What political and social situations did the community face? What do Rwandans need? All of these are the government's role and we all have to obey the laws of the government, established by God as a blessing to human beings, to protect us against the great evil of anarchy (Closson, 2015). However, although respondents may be misunderstood to think that this might be a resistance to change, (Closson, 2015) is so clear that Christians should also seek to influence governments for good, as they have positively influenced civil governments throughout history. In this regard, researcher sought to explore further horizons on the question.

Majority of respondent (48%) ranked the education requirements as the first challenges that ministers face where trying to establish a church ministry in Rwanda. This data aligns well with the study findings that majority (63.3%) of Christian leaders had not received any form of academic theology education prior to starting/ engaging in Christian Ministry.

Many of illiterate pastors have been claiming to have a divine call which motivates them to minister for the sinners. According to them, education is not a problem as Jesus himself didn't attend any school, yet He leads the whole world. Jeremy (2018) goes on to say that there is lack of love among the so called literate; he distinguishes a clear difference between information and understanding as if illiterate preachers are transmitting heavenly information. In Jeremy's (2018) own words: *"Have you ever noticed that those who talk most about the lack of biblical literacy in*

the church today are those who get paid to raise the level of biblical literacy in the church today? That should raise some red flags.” Other claims that the accusation of "illiteracy" is often only a way to ignore or annul the people with whom you disagree so that you do not have to examine their arguments or seek to understand their position (Stetzer, 2019). According to Mitchell (2002): *“I think what we should be asking people about is not biblical literacy or biblical trivia, but biblical love, or divine call and true discipleship character”*. Pastors would go on to say that even Jesus and Paul argued against Biblical literacy when He said: *“You search the Scriptures, for in them you think you have eternal life; and these are they which testify of Me”*³ Paul also says: *“Knowledge puffs up, but love edifies”*⁴ and later that even if we have all knowledge, and understand all mysteries, and can speak in other languages, but have not love, all that knowledge is nothing (1 Cor 13:1-3). Maybe we could add quoting Bible verses, knowing Bible facts, and scoring 100% on a Bible trivia test. These things are nothing without love. This might be a growing debate in Rwanda where the government also emphasizes that Christian leaders should have a degree in theology, but pastors emphasize that the call of Christ is sufficient to lead a Christian ministry rather than schooling. For Christians, there is a growing debate that pastors are plundering the gospel by seeking only to collect money from offerings.

However, Theron (2013) clearly asserts that education is very essential as it contributes to the moral formation of Christian leaders in societies where corruption and immorality are endemic. According to him, the education of Christian leaders contributes not only to the general acquisition of knowledge, but also to their moral formation in particular. As a result, it could contribute to the transformation of the societies in which they live and minister. Ryan Nelson (2018) emphasizes

³ John 5:39

⁴ 1 Corinthians 8:1

also that Ministers must have a deep understanding of biblical doctrine, the role of the church, philosophy and the history of religion. To obtain this education, pastors must obtain at least a bachelor's degree in religious studies, religious education or theology. During these programs, students take courses on the mystery of God, world religions, religious ethics, marriage and the church, as well as the Old and New Testaments. Although, no biblical statement that called ministers to study at a certain level, Closson (2015) is so keen that we much obey to civil government as they have been established by God for our protection. Similarly, Kelly (2018) says that *“we must live in such a way that no one will stumble because of us, and no one will find fault with our ministry. In everything we do, we show that we are true ministers of God”*⁵. 2 Corinthians 6:3-4 again *“See then that ye walk circumspectly, not as fools, but as wise, Redeeming the time, because the days are evil.”* (Ephesians 5:15-16)

Another sizeable number of respondents (28%) indicated that the building standards required by the government in order to start a church ministry is the main challenge. This can also be associated with a lavish emergency of new churches and worship places that caused the government of Rwanda to close more than 6,000 churches, mosques and other places of worship in February 2018, which it deemed in violation of health and safety standards and / or noise pollution ordinances (USA Report 2018, David, 2019).

3.8.2. Influence of theology education and training on the development of Christian Business/ ministry

From the study results 63.3% Christian leaders had not received any form of academic theology education prior to starting/ engaging in Christian Ministry, while only 36.7% had been

⁵ 2 Corinthians 6:3-4

academically trained. This might be the root of the above debate where pastors try to defend themselves. However, fortunately 68.3% of Christian leaders had opportunity to attend a form on theology training after starting/engaging in ministry compared to 31% who had never been trained on theology.

The most critical results here are the fact that Majority of theology students are in school due to the lack of secular education opportunities (33.3%) and the desire to become pastors in their churches (26.67%). In addition, 16.67% of theology students are motivated by meeting the government's training requirements to start their own church ministry. While 13.33% chose theology because of lack of employment, 6.67% wish to supplement their income with a degree in theology. Surprisingly, only 3.33% feel a divine calling to the ministry. Reading this data, one sees the absolute idea of running a ministry as a means of economic prosperity that encourages the use of the gospel and ministry as a means of personal enrichment that has been condemned by Reformer John Calvin (Institutes 4.5.16-18). Although ministers quote Mark 2:25-26; the Bible distinguishes ministry as economic survival from Ministry as economic prosperity:

There is distinction between self-enrichment out of the ministry and being justly rewarded for being in ministry. A basic principle that runs across the Bible is that people have a right to economically survive from their work, including those in ministry. The Torah stated: *“Do not muzzle an ox while it is treading out the grain”* (Deuteronomy 25:4).⁶

This principle was applied to the Levite priests to emphasize that they had to derive an income from their priestly work (Deut 18: 1). Jesus observed the principle of not muzzle the ox while

⁶ Magezi, V. & Banda, C., 2017, ‘Christian ministry and theological education as instruments for economic survival in Africa’, HTS Teologiese Studies/ Theological Studies 73(3), 4545.

sowing the grain in Luke 10: 1-24, when he sent 72 disciples, but forbade them to take provisions, telling them to survive from what their hosts gave them. What should be understood is that the Bible condemns the love of money: “*Keep your lives free from the love of money*” (Hebrews 13:5); in other words, keep your life free from buying into the lies of Man’s Economy and be content with what you have whether a lot or a little. Learning to live in God’s Economy begins by understanding that His economy is made up of the divine integration of the mystery of His lordship, your stewardship, and your generosity. There is a serious gap between spirituality and economic life.

Another important consideration is lack of knowledge in economics and entrepreneurship in different theology curriculums. Majority of respondents (63.33%) find that their programs lack adequate knowledge in economics and entrepreneurship, while 36.67% had these content in their theology programs. This aligns with what Amanze (2008) found that most protestant schools tend to prioritize horizontal piety and lacks a thorough application to political and economic life. However, as mentioned above many theology students have passion for either establishing their own churches or becoming leaders in their current churches. While Money is one of the main topics in the Bible, Christ ministers surrendered to God’s Stewardship should have money management skills. Yet the Bible encourages Christians to invest as much as possible in order to receive an abundant harvest (Matthew 25:24-29).

3.8.3. Christian views about running a ministry for economic prosperity

According to the study results, 41.26% Christian respondents don’t know who takes financial decisions in their churches. This suggests that Christians are not engaged in the management of their churches’ finances and don’t know who their leaders are accountable to. Furthermore, another

sizeable percentage (23.78%) of Christian respondents mentioned that the last word on the church's financial decision is taken by senior pastors. This may, in some cases, suggests the entrepreneurial model of doing church, where the founding prophet or pastor performs the duties of CEO or president of a personal business. In this model of church, the founding leaders are the ambassador of their "brand" model. Therefore, any criticism of the "ministry" or its designated leader is the subject of a strong reaction, because it is ultimately an attack against the brand. It can be noted that church leaders adhering to the entrepreneurial model of ministry exercise an oligarchic style of leadership that logically reduces the faithful to the conveniences of leaders while leaving leaders accountable only to themselves (Banda 2016; Banda & Senokoane 2009; (Biri, 2012); Maxwell 2006; Togarasei 2005). Yet, Ministry is God's and not ours. We are stewards, yet stewardship doesn't mean ownership but management. Thus, it is required in stewards, that a man be found faithful (I Corinthians 4:2). Jesus reflected on this when He told a parable in Matthew 25:14-30 about servants whose master gave them resources called "talents." They were told to be good stewards and use the funds transparently and wisely.

On the other hand, majority of respondents (84.62%) understand that the accumulation of money is condemned by the Bible, while only 15.38% contracted the statement. According to Angel (2013), preachers of the prosperity gospel tell their Christians that the Bible condemns the accumulation of wealth with the intention of asking them to make sacrificial offerings. They would describe money as a source of all evil, with the intention of making their followers Malachi 3: 10-12 Christians whose rooms are too small to handle the blessings.

Finally, considering that Majority of Christian respondents (59.44%) agreed that giving to pastors unlocks the blessings of riches, while 40.56% disagreed on this statement; once may confirm the existence of the above teachings. Unfortunately, what Angel (2013) observed is that

these prosperity pastors play a mediating power asking Christians to bring them extremely high offerings to win God's favor, but they would not even teach their followers how to make money.

IV. Conclusions and Recommendations

4.1. Christian ministries and social, political and economic factors

The finding of this study have confirmed that Christian leaders in Rwanda face a variety of real barriers ranging from discouraging social environment, unfavorable government policies and regulations as well as low level of education and poverty among others. As Closson (2015) puts it, God has established civil government as a blessing for human beings, to protect us from the great evil of anarchy. Governments must punish evil and encourage good by doing justice to the unjust and defending the weak and defenseless. God is sovereign over all nations even today. Citizens should obey the laws of the government, except in certain circumstances.

It is important that governments preserve human freedom, which is essential for human fulfillment on the earth. However, the government cannot save people or fundamentally change human hearts. With regard to the relationship between Church and State, the Church should not govern "*things that belong to Caesar*" and the civil government should not govern "*things that belong to God*". Civil governments should never try to coerce religion, but should protect freedom of religion. Governments should, however, support and encourage religious groups in good faith in general. It is wise that governments establish a strong and clear separation of powers, and even leaders must be subject to the rule of law. Governments should be chosen with the consent of the people. Nations must value patriotism. Rwanda Christians should seek to influence government for good, as Christians have positively influenced civil governments throughout history.

4.2. Influence of theology education and training on the development of Christian Business/ ministry

The results of the study confirmed that theological education could potentially influence the development of Christian ministry; but the majority of those interviewed were unfortunately both academically and biblically illiterate. Furthermore, due to the sacrificial nature of ministry, the majority of theology students are in school due to the lack of other secular education opportunities (33.3%) and the desire to become pastors in their churches (26, 67%). Sadly, and very surprisingly only 3.33% of theology students feel a divine call to ministry. Again, it is unfortunate that the majority of respondents (63.33%) find that their theology programs lack sufficient knowledge in economics and entrepreneurship, the content that would allow them to start and successfully run their secular businesses or the Ministries.

A good theology of work must be accompanied by an economic culture. This requires that theological education opens ministers to the socio-economic and political dynamics that foster endemic intergenerational poverty in Rwanda. This theological education will allow ministers to strengthen the human agency of their communities. This means that theological education must be contextualized in the realities of Rwandans in order to transform them. The implications of this are that theological programs cannot be abstract but must deal with real contextual problems (Chitando, 2010 ; Haddad, 2016; Oliver 2016). Although this is beginning to happen in Rwanda, it is insufficient, as much of the religious studies in Rwanda are conducted from a phenomenological perspective, which often fails to understand the socio-economic and political implications of Christian doctrines. In a context of poverty in Rwanda, theological education must be conducted from an entrepreneurial and developmental perspective. Further research is needed to determine what such a theological program should look like.

4.3. Christian views about running a ministry for economic prosperity

The results confirmed that traces of prosperity Gospel preachers exist in Rwanda; many pastors tending to manage the church and ministries as their own properties. They would try to create a gap where they are accountable to none, leaving the majority of Christian ignorant of how and who takes financial decisions on the ministry finances. They tend to make themselves mediator and convince Christians that money is source of all evil, hence ask Christians to give to pastor in order to attract God's blessings.

The discussion in this study highlights the practices of contemporary Pentecostal / Charismatic churches are symptomatic of commercialization and commodification of religion. The study showed how some Pentecostals /Charismatic churches with their theology of prosperity gospel-material wealth and well-being highlighted in salvation, incorporate aggressive advertising strategy and branding strategy to make religion appeal to the masses whose hope is lost in an austere economic context environment. Such Pentecostal / Charismatic churches, with their doctrine of salvation and ritual practice (healing and deliverance), provide members with tools to respond to the vagaries of the socio-economic crisis situation and challenges of life. In doing so, they emphasize a post-modern conception of religion that favors religions personalization characterized by the individual choice of doctrine and practice.

Again, although the emphasis on religion's ability to alleviate life's difficulties makes religion a kind of market product, it does have some socio-economic implications. An important aspect is that in this way the neo-Pentecostal / charismatic churches have been able to raise huge sums of money and have engaged in the redistribution of their wealth in areas such as education and health care. However, the capitalistic practices of some Pentecostal / Charismatic churches also have very

negative implications for the practice of religion and Christianity in general. Indeed, it devalues the Christian commitment and makes the relationship with God a mere contractual market relationship (Benyah, 2018).

As Horsfield (1984, p. 84) suggests from a North American context, the insistence that people might purchase religious goods or sow a seed in order to be blessed, saved, or prosperous may very easily lead to a *“return to the purchasing of indulgencies, with the only proviso being one’s willingness to pay the required amount in order to set the mechanisms of miracle-working in motion”*. The result is that the poor, the excluded, the marginalized and the socially disadvantaged or destitute, who were really at the center of the Lord Jesus Christ's ministry, are ignored because they may not have the means to buy their healing and also, can be overlooked because they do not show the symbols and good images of the gospel of prosperity. This means that they will also lose all types of social capital, social cohesion and reproduction that are necessary ingredients for socio-economic well-being, development and transformation.

God is not against money but against the love of money. He gives us the wealth not to build great houses and to live in luxury, but to become his stewards. Stewardship is about management and not the ownership; that is why a steward is the person who manages the property, finances and the home of another person. Christian leaders should know that we are stewards or managers of what God has placed in our trust. They should teach Christians that God is always looking for people He can trust with large sums of money to build His Kingdom. Stewardship is a call of God for His people to assist in managing the affairs of the earth with Him. That has always been His plan from the beginning of creation and it has never changed. A steward is someone who does not do anything for himself or herself but does that for another. If you are doing things for yourself, you have missed what God wants for your life. Our purpose and calling is to finance the

advancement of the Kingdom of God. Knowing God's purpose and plan helps us establish proper priorities for our life and ministry. However, we are accountable not only for knowing God's will for our life and ministry, but also for doing it. We are living in the last days and the gospel is going to be preached in every nation. We are going to see millions upon millions of souls come to salvation and to the knowledge of Jesus Christ.

4.4. Recommendations

The results of the findings have been discussed and it is in light of this that the following recommendations are made:

- Poverty which is responsible for the spread of the prosperity gospel must be curbed even though its eradication is impossible. Practically, it is recommended that the government and other stakeholders put in place poverty alleviation programs and work hard to ensure that these programs achieve their objectives. It has also been observed that the gap between the rich and the poor in Rwanda is getting wider and wider, and if this trend is allowed to persist, poverty will continue to make life miserable for people. Consequently, it is imperative for the extant government to take the bold step of cutting down on the salaries of political office holders and their appendages and ensure that public funds are used discreetly to gradually and systematically lift the poor out of their state of deprivation.
- Illiteracy has been identified to be a factor responsible for the spread of the prosperity gospel; hence it is recommended that the government should do their best to curb illiteracy by sustaining the program of free and compulsory basic education and also consider the benefits of introducing free and compulsory adult literacy programs.

- It is also recommended that prosperity preachers be intimated on the futility of living in opulence. They should meditate on the fact that ‘we have brought nothing into this world and neither can we carry anything out when we inevitably expire’. They should stop making their members base their hope on false promises but teach them the need for hard work and contentment and the joy that comes from assisting fellow humans in need.
- Professed Christians who attend prosperity churches and are literate in any of the languages in which the Bible is available should take time to study it. They should be encouraged to engage in Bible discussions with professed Christians from other denominations and with an open mind as this can draw their attention to parts of the Bible that debunk the prosperity gospel. Most importantly, they should withdraw from churches whose teachings cannot at all be reconciled with the tenets of the Holy Scriptures.
- As believers, we are all stewards of spiritual resources God gives us which include⁷:
 - **The Gospel:** Every believer is a steward of the Gospel. We are to share its message with others.
 - **Finances:** Every believer is a steward of the money God gives to him personally. Those who handle ministry funds of a church or Christian organization are also stewards of these funds.
 - **Material Resources of Ministry:** Such as church buildings, property, and equipment.

⁷ Thomas Nelson 1979, 1980, 1982. Management by objectives: Inc., Publishers. Page 2

- **Spiritual Gifts:** Each believer has at least one spiritual gift. You are a steward of your spiritual gift and your place of ministry in the Body of Christ.
- **Other Believers:** God uses people, not programs, to build His Kingdom. Management or stewardship involves people. If you are a leader, you are responsible for the people who work with you in ministry. You are to help them grow spiritually and develop their own spiritual gifts for the work of the ministry.

Therefore, we should not do thing for our own interest. When people do not understand God's purpose and their specific purpose within God's plan, it is difficult to plan. We [Christian leaders] must first know our purpose if we are to make plans to fulfill it. God especially anoints and uses those who bring their own life purpose and ministry plans in harmony with His purpose and plans. When we do not understand God's purpose, we are not in harmony with His plan. This is why many ministries fail.

V. Appendices

5.1. Questionnaire for active Christians in Nyanza

Questions	Objective:	1	Examine the social, political and economic factors that influence the Christian ministries in Rwanda
		1	How would you do rate the regulatory challenges ministers face when starting a Christian Ministry. (Education requirements, Building standards, Registration procedures, acceptance, other)
		2	What is the perception of your social environment in relation to the commitment in unpaid Christian ministry?

Questions	3	Do you see / do you think there are government regulations that Christians have difficulty coping with when setting up / running a church / Christian ministry? What changes are needed in government policies and regulations in order to make them friendly to Christian Ministers? -FGD
	Objective:	2 Examine the influence of theology education and training on the development of Christian business /ministry
	1	Prior to starting your church/ ministry, had you received any form theology education at any academic institution?
	2	Have you ever been through any kind of theology training program since you began your ministry?
	3	In your own opinion, at what level of schooling do you think it is appropriate to become a Christian Leader?
Questions	4	What motivated you to study theology? (Lack of job, lack of other secular education opportunity, to be able to start my own church, to supplement income, Divine vocation, to become a pastor in my church, Other)
	5	Does your theology program include enough courses in economics and entrepreneurship that could allow a graduate to start / run a successful business in a secular world?
	Objective:	3 Understand Christian views about running a ministry for economic prosperity
	1	To your knowledge, in your church, who is the financial decision-maker(s)?
	2	To your knowledge, does the Bible condemns the accumulation of money?
	3	As a believer, can you agree that giving God's anointed people, like pastors, brings more blessing from God?

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